

Approach to Alopecia in Dogs in Clinical Practice

Büşra UZUN*

Department of Internal Medicine, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Ondokuz Mayıs,
Samsun, Türkiye

busra.uzun@omu.edu.tr

ORCID: 0000-0002-4314-6814

Basım/Published: 25.07.2025

How to cite: Uzun, B (2025) Approach to Alopecia in Dogs in Clinical Practice *VZS*, *I*(1), 104-118.

Atıf yapmak için: Uzun, B (2025) Klinik Pratikte Köpeklerde Alopesiye Yaklaşım *VZS*, *I*(1), 104-118.

Abstract: Alopecia in companion animals, particularly dogs, represents a complex clinical manifestation with diverse etiologies ranging from infectious agents and endocrine disorders to congenital and hereditary abnormalities. The skin, as the body's largest organ, plays a critical role in maintaining homeostasis, acting as a barrier against environmental insults while contributing to thermoregulation, vitamin D synthesis, and sensory perception. Hair follicles, derived from ectodermal-mesenchymal interactions, are vulnerable to a wide range of pathological insults. Alopecia may be focal or multifocal, and its presentation—symmetrical or asymmetrical—can provide clues to the underlying pathology. Common causes include bacterial folliculitis, dermatophytosis, demodicosis, and various autoimmune or hormonal imbalances. Congenital and hereditary forms, such as ectodermal dysplasia and color dilution alopecia, are breed-specific and often diagnosed via skin biopsy and histopathology. Among acquired causes, endocrine disorders like hypothyroidism, hyperadrenocorticism, and hyperestrogenism disrupt normal follicular cycling and keratinization, resulting in progressive alopecia. Follicular dysplasias and alopecia X, although primarily cosmetic in nature, remain diagnostic and therapeutic challenges due to their unclear pathogenesis. Management strategies are etiology-specific and include antiparasitic, antimicrobial, hormonal, and palliative treatments such as melatonin or essential fatty acids. A detailed clinical history, dermatological examination, and targeted diagnostics are essential to guide treatment and provide prognosis.

Keywords: Alopecia, endocrine dermatopathies, follicular dysplasia, hair follicle disorders, skin diseases

Klinik Pratikte Köpeklerde Alopesiye Yaklaşım

Özet: Evcil hayvanlarda, özellikle köpeklerde alopesi, enfeksiyöz etkenlerden endokrin bozukluklara, konjenital ve kalıtsal anormalliklere kadar çeşitli etiyolojilere sahip karmaşık bir

linik tablodur. Vücudun en büyük organı olan deri, homeostazinin korunmasında hayati bir rol oynar; voltaj değişimine karşı bariyer oluşturma, termoregülasyon, D vitamini sentezi ve duyuşsal algı gibi kapasitenin yerine getirilmesi. Ektodermal-mezenkimal etkileşimlerle kıl folikülleri, çeşitli problemlere karşı hassastır. Alopesinin fokal veya multifokal olması, simetrik veya asimetrik olması, altta yatan patolojiye dair ipuçları verebilir. En yaygın nedenler arasında kapsamlı folikülit, dermatofitoz, demodikozis ve çeşitli otoimmün ya da hormonal dengesizlikler yer alır. Ektodermal displazi ve renk kaybı alopesisi gibi doğuştan ve kalıtsal formlar, ırka özgüdür ve sıklıkla deri biyopsisi ve histopatoloji ile teşhis edilir. Edinsel nedenler arasında hipotiroidizm, hiperadrenokortisizm ve hiperöstrojenizm gibi endokrin bozuklukları normal foliküler döngüyü ve keratinizasyonu bozarak ilerleyici kıl kaybına neden olur. Foliküler displaziler ve alopesi X, esas olarak kozmetik nitelikte olmalarına rağmen, patogenezinin belirsiz olması nedeniyle tanı ve tedavide zorluklar yaratmaya devam etmektedir. Tedavi, etiyo­lojiye özgü olarak; antiparaziter, antimikrobiyal, hormonal ya da melatonin ve esansiyel yağ asitleri gibi palyatif tedavileri içerir. Ayrıntılı klinik öykü, dermatolojik muayene ve hedefe yönelik tanı yöntemleri, tedaviyi yönlendirmede ve prognoz belirlemede kritik sistemlere sahiptir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Alopesi, deri hastalıkları, endokrin dermatopatiler, foliküler displazi, kıl folikülü hastalıkları

INTRODUCTION

All mammals, even marine mammals, have varying amounts of hair on their skin. The skin serves a vital role in life. It serves as an anatomical and physiological barrier between the animal and its environment. This function prevents the loss of fluids, electrolytes, and macromolecules from the body, while also preventing the entry of physical, chemical, and microbiological agents from the environment (Menon et al., 2022). Its flexibility, elasticity, and durability allow for movement and give the body shape and form. Body temperature regulation is achieved through hair, cutaneous blood flow, and sweat glands. Skin also allows for the storage of electrolytes, water, vitamins, fats, carbohydrates, proteins, and other substances. The skin is the primary sensory organ for detecting touch, pressure, heat, cold, pain, and itch. Vitamin D is produced in the skin by the stimulating effects of sunlight (Visha et al., 2023).

- The skin (cutis) is the largest organ covering the body's exterior. It also serves as a marker for potential internal organ disease. The skin has many functions. These include:
- It protects the organism against physical, chemical, and biological effects.

- It prevents the loss of water, electrolytes, and macromolecules.
- It protects the organism against the harmful effects of ultraviolet rays with the melanin pigment synthesized by epidermal cells.
- It provides the flexibility necessary for movement.
- It synthesizes vitamin D.
- It has antibacterial and antifungal activity (Jackson et al., 2012).

Hair Follicle Anatomy and Cycle

Hairs are flexible epidermal structures embedded in the skin. Hair follicles form during embryonic development through complex interactions between mesenchymal and ectodermal cells (Jackson et al. 2012). The abundance of hairs and the rate of growth vary depending on age, gender, and body parts. Hair does not grow simultaneously everywhere on the body, nor does hair growth in the same location.

A hair consists of a root (*radix pili*), a portion that protrudes from the skin (*scapus pili*), and a tip (*apex pili*).

The deepest part of the hair follicle, embedded in the dermis, is the *bulbus pili*. The protruding structures within the *bulbus pili* are called *papillae pili*. The epithelial structure covering the *papillae* is called *matrix pili*. Melanocytes within the *papillae* produce the hair pigment.

The hair shaft consists of three interlocking layers. From outside to inside: cuticle, cortex, and medulla. The cuticle is the outermost layer of the hair. Just below the cuticle is the cortex layer (Welle, 2023). It forms the core of the hair. Its tonofibrils provide strength and melanin pigment gives the hair its color. The medulla is the innermost layer of the hair. This layer is not found in all hairs.

ALOPECIA

Alopecia is a disease characterized by thinning, partial, or complete alopecia in areas with normal hair growth. It can occur in cats and dogs of all ages and breeds. It can progress gradually or acutely. Any disease that affects the hair follicles can cause

alopecia. Some diseases can damage the hair follicle or the hair shaft, inhibiting hair growth. Alopecia can be infectious or noninfectious (de Sousa et al., 2022).

Symptoms of alopecia in animals may include:

- Focal, multifocal, or generalized alopecia
- Alopecia around the eyes and mouth
- Flaking skin
- Asymmetrical alopecia
- Symmetrical alopecia on both sides of the body
- Alopecia caused by itching, biting, or scratching

A detailed history and physical examination are required for an accurate diagnosis of alopecia (Welle and Dominique, 2016).

Focal and Multifocal Alopecia

Alopecia can be focal or multifocal. We can distinguish between focal and multifocal alopecia. Focal alopecia is usually limited to a specific area or spot on the body. Multifocal alopecia, on the other hand, means that more than one area of the body is affected. Multifocal alopecia can be symmetrical (on both sides and in similar locations) or asymmetrical (not uniform and present on both sides) (Jackson et al., 2012)

Focal Alopecia

Differential diagnoses for focal alopecia include:

- Bacterial Folliculitis
- Demodicosis
- Dermatophytosis
- Secondary bacterial or fungal infections secondary to trauma (less common)
- Drug reactions (less common)

Skin scrapings, skin cytology, culture, and/or biopsy can be helpful in managing these cases. Once the cause is identified, antiparasitic, antifungal, or antibacterial agents should be administered (Jackson et al., 2012).

Multifocal Alopecia

The differential diagnosis for multifocal alopecia is extensive. Some of the more common etiologies include:

- Primary alopecia conditions of congenital or hereditary origin
- Secondary alopecia resulting from pruritic skin diseases
- Endocrinopathies
- Hereditary Conditions

In dogs, alopecia can occur secondary to hereditary dermatological conditions, including the following:

- Canine ectodermal dysplasia
- Canine familial dermatomyositis: A hereditary condition of the skin and/or muscle that affects collie dogs, Shetland sheepdogs, and their crossbreeds.

When a hereditary skin condition is suspected, the most useful diagnostic test is a skin biopsy. Multiple biopsy samples are often required to establish a diagnosis. It is recommended that biopsy samples be sent to dermatohistopathology.

Congenital Alopecia

Congenital alopecia, which is the partial or total absence of hair, is a rare condition. Congenital alopecia is usually associated with abnormalities of other ectodermally derived skin appendages (e.g., epitrichous and atrial glands, claws, etc.) and teeth. This condition has been reported occasionally in some breeds (Jackson et al., 2012). This condition is characteristic of breeds such as the Mexican Hairless Dog, Peruvian Hairless Dog, and Chinese Crested Dog. This phenotype in the hairless dog is classified as "canine ectodermal dysplasia" because these dogs also have missing or abnormally shaped teeth (Jackson et al., 2012)

This ectodermal defect is inherited from offspring as a monogenic autosomal semi-dominant trait linked to chromosome 17 in three breeds. Heterozygous dogs are hairless, and homozygous mutants die during embryogenesis (Marín-García and Llobat, 2022)

Acquired Alopecia

Hypothyroidism

Hypothyroidism is a hormonal deficiency resulting from decreased production and secretion of thyroid hormones. It is a very common hormonal disorder in dogs. Thyroid hormone is required for the initiation of anagen hair follicles, regulation of keratinization, sebaceous gland secretion, and control of bacterial flora. Hypothyroidism is most commonly seen in medium-sized, older dogs (3-6 years) (Jaiswal et al., 2018).

Clinical Appearance

It causes the formation of dry, dull, and brittle hair that breaks easily. Early signs of the disease include dryness of the skin and hair coat and non-itchy alopecia. Alopecia is usually seen bilaterally and symmetrically in the dorsal region of the neck, ventral and lateral thorax, abdomen, and tail (Figure 1). Alopecia in the caudal region is very characteristic and is referred to as rat tail (Frank, 2006). Other findings include alopecia on the nose, hyperpigmentation and alopecia, weight gain despite decreased appetite, lethargy, and hyperkeratosis (Jackson et al., 2012). Guard hairs often appear dry, brittle, and dull, lacking vitality. Sometimes these guard hairs are lost and replaced by very fine, delicate hairs. If the hair does not grow after being shaved for any reason, hypothyroidism should be considered first (Kumar and Srikala, 2013). Dry or oily seborrhea is commonly noted.

Figure 1. Rat-tailed appearance in a Golden Retriever with hypothyroidism (Jackson et al., 2012)

Treatment

Lifelong treatment with levothyroxine is necessary. Treatment is administered orally at a dose of 20 µg/kg q12h (or 0.5 mg/m² q12h). Lethargy may resolve within a

few days, but hair growth may take several months to return (Jackson et al., 2012). After 4-8 weeks of levothyroxine replacement therapy or after clinical symptoms have resolved, serum TT4 concentrations should be measured 4-6 hours after the pill to determine if the hormone level is adequate.

Hyperadrenocorticism

Spontaneous and iatrogenic hyperadrenocorticism are common disorders in dogs. Spontaneous hyperadrenocorticism results from excessive circulating cortisol. Eighty-five percent of dogs with spontaneous hyperadrenocorticism have pituitary-mediated hyperadrenocorticism. The remaining 15% are caused by an adrenal gland tumor that secretes excessive amounts of cortisol (Jackson et al., 2012). These two types of hyperadrenocorticism are clinically indistinguishable. Spontaneous hyperadrenocorticism is more common in middle-aged dogs than in older dogs. Excessive glucocorticoid use also causes iatrogenic hyperadrenocorticism. The onset of clinical signs is insidious and slow. In this endocrine disorder, bilateral symmetric alopecia in the abdomen is also observed (Figure 2). Pituitary hyperadrenocorticism is more common in small breeds and has no gender predisposition. Adrenal hypothyroidism is more common in large breeds and 2/3 of the cases are female (Galac et al., 2008).

Figure 2. Bilateral symmetric alopecia in the abdomen due to hyperadrenocorticism (Mecklenburg et al., 2009)

Clinical Appearance

All clinical findings in hyperadrenocorticism are caused by excess circulating cortisol. The most common symptoms are polydipsia (>100 ml/kg) and polyuria (>50 ml/kg) (McGrotty and Randell, 2019). Other findings include polyphagia, lethargy, rapid breathing, muscle wasting, abdominal enlargement, and in some cases, neurological findings secondary to a pituitary tumor, testicular atrophy, and anoestrus (Jackson et al.,

2012). Abdominal enlargement occurs due to muscle weakness, liver enlargement, and fat accumulation in the abdomen. Because it develops slowly, patients may not notice it.

Treatment

In patients suspected of having hyperadrenocorticism, a complete blood count, serum biochemistry, and urine analysis should be performed. ACTH stimulation tests should be performed to assess adrenal levels and adjust treatment. Patient survival may vary depending on the tumor type and the medication used (Barker et al., 2005). Treatment options include mitotane, trilostane, and retinoic acid. Other medications have not been found to be effective.

Mitotane: Mitotane, an insecticide, is a widely used medication for pituitary hyperadrenocorticism. It is also used as an alternative to adrenalectomy in the treatment of adrenal tumors. Due to the long duration of treatment with mitotane, careful monitoring is necessary, as its use can lead to Addison's disease (Miura et al., 2022). Appetite and water intake are the best indicators for assessing mitotane's effectiveness. Therefore, the owner should carefully monitor appetite and water intake before and after treatment. Treatment-related side effects are related to decreased cortisol levels. These include drowsiness, weakness, diarrhea, and vomiting. If such side effects occur, mitotane use should be discontinued and prednisone (0.25 mg/kg orally) should be administered for 1 week (Haider et al., 2021)

Trilostane: Trilostane is a synthetic steroid with no hormonal activity. Trilostane inhibits the release of steroids not only from the adrenal glands but also from the gonadal organs and uterus. In pituitary hyperadrenocorticism, ACTH secretion and adrenal hyperplasia persist. It has fewer side effects than mitotane. In most cases, symptoms are mild and resolve when treatment is discontinued. These symptoms are related to hypoadrenocorticism. Diarrhea, pancreatitis, and, rarely, death may occur (Golinelli et al., 2021).

Hyperestrogenism in Female Dogs

It is a disease caused by high estrogen levels in female dogs. Estrogens are powerful hair growth stimulants. Cystic ovaries or functional ovarian tumors cause abnormal estrogen levels. Hormonal imbalances disrupt normal hair follicle cycling and

cause alopecia. Increased estrogen delays the anagen phase by halting the telogen phase (Neubert et al., 2023).

Clinical Appearance

Dermatological findings of hyperestrogenism include hyperpigmentation in the perineal and genital areas and alopecia that progresses from back to front (Jackson et al., 2012). Initially, bilateral symmetrical alopecia is observed in the perineum, inguinal region, and the groin area. Hairs break off easily when pulled. There is enlargement of the nipples and vulva. Hyperpigmentation is present in the affected areas. Comedones are observed in the vulvar skin (Kürşat Hoca's book). Bone marrow toxicity and non-regenerative anemia develop in chronic hyperestrogenism (Cerundolo, 2023).

Treatment

Treatment involves ovariectomy. The prognosis is good. Hair regrowth and skin healing take 3-4 months (Cerundolo, 2023).

Follicular Dysplasia

The term follicular dysplasia covers a number of alopecia areas related to skin color, including the following diseases: (Jackson et al., 2012).

1. Color-related follicular dysplasias:

- a) Color dilution alopecia
- b) Black hair follicle dysplasia
- c) Follicle absence in red or black Dobermans
- d) Follicle steatosis in Rottweilers

2-Follicular dysplasias not linked to color:

- a) Alopecia X
- b) Breed-linked follicular dysplasia
- c) Recurrent flank alopecia in dogs

Color-Dependent Follicular Dysplasia

Diagnosis of diseases in this category is made by microscopic examination of the hair and skin histopathology. Clinical signs depend on the color and breed predisposition of the young animal, along with alopecia or progressive hypotrichosis. Microscopic examination of the hair reveals numerous large melanin clusters and broken hairs in the cortex and medulla of the hair in the affected area (Kamel et al., 2021).

Color Dilution Alopecia

This is an autosomal recessive and hereditary disease. Alopecia is often accompanied by the disease. The disease is most commonly seen in Doberman Pinschers. However, it has also been reported in breeds such as Yorkshire terriers, Dachshunds, miniature Pinschers, Chow Chows, and Chihuahuas. Certain common coat colors, such as blue, red, fawn, and gray, are identified as color dilution alopecia in these breeds. These colors are called dilution because they are lighter shades of black or brown (Caramalac et al., 2021).

Clinical Findings

The first clinical signs appear between 3 months and 3 years of age. Affected dogs are prone to secondary bacterial folliculitis. Comedones are also present in the affected area (Jackson et al., 2012).

Treatment

Melatonin, retinoids, or essential fatty acids can be tried as palliative treatments to improve hair and skin condition. Antibiotics should be administered in cases of pyoderma, which is often associated with follicular keratosis. Topical shampoos and moisturizers can be helpful in reducing the severity of the disease (Jackson et al., 2012).

Alopecia X

The etiology of alopecia remains unclear. Alopecia X is a disease characterized by bilateral symmetric alopecia in adult dogs, the etiology and pathogenesis of which have not yet been elucidated (Crawford et al., 2024). The disease has previously been referred to as:

- Pseudo-Cushing's disease

- Adult-onset growth hormone deficiency
- Growth hormone-responsive alopecia
- Adrenal gland sex hormone imbalance
- Dog-like adrenal gland hyperplasia syndrome
- Follicular dysplasia of Nordic breeds

Follicular growth disorder of breeds with plush hair coats (Jackson et al., 2012). Genetic predisposition to hormone production disorders or abnormal hormonal effects on hair follicles are suspected in its pathogenesis. It is more common in Nordic breed dogs and adults between 1 and 3 years of age. It is more common in intact male dogs. Following neutering, hair growth may occur, but the disease may recur within 1-2 years (Welle, 2023).

Clinical Findings

The disease was previously called Cushing's syndrome because its clinical findings resembled Cushing's syndrome. However, there is no biochemical abnormality. Increased matting of the hair coat is an early clinical finding in affected owners. Sometimes, the overall loss of the hair coat can lead to a "puppy-dog" appearance (Figure 3). The hair may appear lighter or a different color as the protective layer is shed. The animals are in good health. If there are signs of systemic disease, conditions such as hyperadrenocorticism, hypothyroidism, hyperestrogenism, and diabetes mellitus should be considered and investigated. Sebaceous adenitis can be distinguished by a skin biopsy. Primary alopecia occurs initially on the neck, tail, caudo-dorsal, and buttock areas (Zanna et al., 2024). Hair on the head and legs does not fall out immediately. Secondary hair also falls out over time, resulting in a complete alopecia and a puppy-dog appearance. Hyperpigmentation is often observed on the skin. However, not every patient experiences hyperpigmentation. Increased pigmentation is likely a result of sunlight exposure. This can be minimized by restricting sunlight or clothing (Welle, 2023).

Figure 3. A Pomerian with alopecia X linked generalized alopecia (Mecklenburg et al., 2009).

Treatment

Alopecia X is a cosmetic condition. Because it doesn't cause any general deterioration, treatment is offered if the owner wishes. It should also be kept in mind that treatment can have side effects (Kaya et al., 2025). Various medical and surgical procedures are recommended. Spaying is recommended first because it promotes hair growth. Mitotane has also been reported to be effective. It should be used with caution considering the side effects of mitotane and possible hypoadrenocorticism (Jackson et al., 2009). Mitotane is recommended when other medications fail. Mitotane causes selective atrophy of the zona fasciculata and zona reticularis in the adrenal cortex. It is started at a dose of 15-25 mg/kg po once daily. It is then continued twice weekly. Treatment is discontinued when hair regrowth occurs. It is resumed when alopecia develops. An ACTH stimulation test should be performed to determine whether hypoadrenocorticism has occurred. Melatonin causes partial or complete hair regrowth in 40% of cases. It is quite safe. Melatonin is administered at a dose of 3 mg twice daily PO for dogs weighing less than 15 kg and 6-12 mg twice daily PO for dogs weighing more than 15 kg for 3 months. Treatment is stopped when hair regrowth occurs and resumed when alopecia develops. Trilostane has been reported to increase hair growth in Pomeranians and miniature Poodles. Recently, antiandrogens (finasteride) have also been used in the treatment of Alopecia X (de Sousa et al., 2022).

Recurrent Flank Alopecia in Dogs

Recurrent flank alopecia in dogs is a disease characterized by bilateral, symmetrical alopecia on the trunk, usually occurring seasonally.

The exact cause is unknown, but its seasonal recurrence suggests that photoperiod may play a role (Verschuuren et al., 2024). The disease can occur once or twice a year or regularly. In most dogs, alopecia begins between November and March in the Northern Hemisphere.

Clinical Findings

Hyperpigmentation and alopecia are most commonly found in the thoracolumbar region, but can also be seen on the upper nose, around the base of the ears, and at the base of the tail. Some breeds are more likely to experience this condition. Boxers account for approximately half of all cases (Jackson et al., 2012).

Treatment

In most dogs, hair grows back naturally after 3-8 months. Even if the hair doesn't grow, it doesn't affect the animal's quality of life. Treatment can be considered if the owner wishes. Half of the cases respond to melatonin. Dogs weighing less than 10 kg are given 3-6 mg once or twice daily, PO, for 1-2 months, and dogs weighing more than 10 kg are given 6 mg once or twice daily, PO, for 1-2 months (Verschuuren et al., 2022).

CONCLUSION

Alopecia in dogs is a multifactorial dermatological condition that requires a systematic and etiologically guided diagnostic approach. Accurate diagnosis depends on thorough clinical evaluation and appropriate laboratory or histopathological tests. While some forms of alopecia are cosmetic and benign, others may signal serious underlying endocrine or systemic diseases. A clear understanding of the hair follicle cycle, associated disorders, and breed predispositions is essential for effective case management. Early diagnosis and individualized treatment protocols not only improve clinical outcomes but also enhance the quality of life for affected animals and their owners.

REFERENCES

Barker, E. N., Campbell, S., Tebb, A. J., Neiger, R., Herrtage, M. E., Reid, S. W. J., & Ramsey, I. K. (2005). A comparison of the survival times of dogs treated with mitotane or trilostane for pituitary-dependent hyperadrenocorticism. *Journal of Veterinary Internal Medicine*, 19(6), 810-815.

- Caramalac, S. M., Caramalac, S. M., Babo-Terra, V. J., Ramos, C. A., & Palumbo, M. I. (2021). PCR-RFLP molecular confirmation of color dilution alopecia in dogs in Brazil. *Journal of Veterinary Diagnostic Investigation*, 33(5), 984-986.
- Cerundolo, R. (2023). The effect of endocrine disease on the skin. In *BSAVA Manual of Canine and Feline Endocrinology* (pp. 54-61). BSAVA Library.
- Crawford, M., Lundberg, A., & Neto, R. (2024). Canine alopecia X-Like disorder. *Brazilian Journal of Veterinary Pathology*, 17(1), 76-78.
- de Sousa Ferreira, M. A., de Carvalho, V. M., da Silva Dutra, M., Rodrigues, F. R. N., de Araújo Viana, D., & Ferreira, T. C. (2022). Alopecia X in dogs: report of seven cases. *Research, Society and Development*, 11(10), e159111032652-e159111032652
- Frank, L. A. (2006). Comparative dermatology—canine endocrine dermatoses. *Clinics in dermatology*, 24(4), 317-325.
- Galac, S., Kars, V. J., Voorhout, G., Mol, J. A., & Kooistra, H. S. (2008). ACTH-independent hyperadrenocorticism due to food-dependent hypercortisolemia in a dog: a case report. *The Veterinary Journal*, 177(1), 141-143.
- Golinelli, S., De Marco, V., Leal, R. O., Barbarossa, A., Anibaldi, C., Maietti, E., ... & Fracassi, F. (2021). Comparison of methods to monitor dogs with hypercortisolism treated with trilostane. *Journal of Veterinary Internal Medicine*, 35(6), 2616-2627.
- Haider, M. S., Ahmad, T., Groll, J., Scherf-Clavel, O., Kroiss, M., & Luxenhofer, R. (2021). The challenging pharmacokinetics of mitotane: an old drug in need of new packaging. *European Journal of Drug Metabolism and Pharmacokinetics*, 46(5), 575-593.
- Jackson, Hilary A., and Rosanna Marsella (2012). *BSAVA manual of canine and feline dermatology*. 3rd Ed. British Small Animal Veterinary Association, 2012.
- Jaiswal, M., Shukla, P. C., Tiwari, A., Gupta, D., Singh, B., Maravi, P., & Sheikh, A. A. (2018). Recent approaches in diagnosis and management of canine hypothyroidism: A review. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 7(1), 90-94.
- Kamel, S. A., Abdou, O. M., Ahmed, K. A., & Farag, H. S. (2021). Hematological, biochemical and histopathological studies on selected canine skin diseases. *Veterinary Medical Journal (Giza)*, 67(1), 69-94.
- Kaya, C., Esin, B., & Esin, Ç. (2025). Evaluation of Testicular Arterial Doppler Ultrasonography and Spermatological Parameters in Pomeranian Dogs with Alopecia X. *Kocatepe Veterinary Journal*, 18(1), 25-32.

Kumar, K. S., & Srikala, D. (2013). Hypothyroidism associated skin and coat abnormalities in dogs-a study of 49 patients.

Marín-García, P. J., & Llobat, L. (2022). Inheritance of monogenic hereditary skin disease and related canine breeds. *Veterinary Sciences*, 9(8), 433.

McGrotty, Y., & Randell, S. (2019). Diagnostic approach to polyuria and polydipsia in dogs. *In Practice*, 41(6), 249-258.

Mecklenburg, L., Linek, M., & Tobin, D. J. (Eds.). (2009). *Hair loss disorders in domestic animals*. John Wiley & Sons.

Menon, G. K., Elias, P. M., Wakefield, J. S., & Crumrine, D. (2022). Cetacean epidermal specialization: A review. *Anatomia, histologia, embryologia*, 51(5), 563-575.

Miura, K., Sunahara, H., Sakai, Y., Isshiki, S., Hasegawa, M., & Oda, M. (2022). Effective treatment with mitotane for a canine case of presumed ectopic Cushing's syndrome-related pheochromocytoma. *Open Veterinary Journal*, 12(5), 762-767.

Neubert, A., Walter, B., & Wildermuth, B. (2023). Hyperestrogenism and hyperandrogenism in dogs and cats due to secondary exposure.

Verschuuren, M. U., Schlotter, Y. M., & Leegwater, P. A. (2024). Investigation of the association of the MLPH gene with seasonal canine flank alopecia in Rhodesian Ridgeback dogs. *Canine medicine and genetics*, 11(1), 5.

Verschuuren, M. U., Schlotter, Y. M., van Geijlswijk, I. M., van Der Lugt, J. J., & Gehring, R. (2022). The efficacy of subcutaneous slow-release melatonin implants in the prevention of canine flank alopecia recurrence is uncertain: A double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled study. *Veterinary Dermatology*, 33(6), 553-558.

Visha, P., Das, P. K., Mukherjee, J., & Banerjee, D. (2023). Special senses. In *Textbook of Veterinary Physiology* (pp. 295-311). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.

Welle, M. M. (2023). Basic principles of hair follicle structure, morphogenesis, and regeneration. *Veterinary pathology*, 60(6), 732-747.

Welle, Monika M., and Dominique J. Wiener (2016). "The hair follicle: a comparative review of canine hair follicle anatomy and physiology." *Toxicologic pathology* 44.4: 564-574.

Zanna, G., Abramo, F., Contiero, B., Zini, E., Albanese, F., Borio, E., ... & Roccabianca, P. (2024). Dermoscopic findings and comparison of usefulness of longitudinal versus transversal sections in the histological diagnosis of alopecia X. *Veterinary Dermatology*, 35(2), 126-137.